

Producer Level Questionnaires FINAL VERSION

Date of the surveyyyyy-mm-dd

Country Benin Tanzania**Province****District****Ward**

Village**Village chair man**

ENUMERATOR*Select your name***Household ID**

Name of Household Head

Questionnaire started on DATE*The date you started the questionnaire*yyyy-mm-dd

Questionnaire started on TIME*Indicate the hour you started the questionnaire*hh:mm

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE PRODUCER (AND THE RESPONDENT)

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE PRODUCER (AND THE RESPONDENT)

Name of the producer

i.e. the person who takes decisions regarding cotton production

Respondent

- Producer
- Somebody else

It is preferred that the cotton producer himself/herself answers this questionnaire. Please check whether it is possible to interview the cotton producer himself/herself, e.g. at another time. Otherwise, please make sure that the respondent is very well informed about the cotton production (decisions) of this producer and answers the questions on his/her behalf.

Name of respondent

Phone number of respondent

Phone number of the producer

Sex of the producer

- Male
- Female

What is cotton producer's relationship to the head of the household?

- Head of the household
- Spouse
- Child
- Grandchild
- Parent/Parent-in-law
- Son/Daughter-in-law
- Adopted/ Foster/Stepchild
- Other relative
- Non-relative

What is the age of the producer?

What proportion of your household's total monetary income comes from your cotton production?

10 stones = all monetary income: how many 'stones' from cotton?

EDUCATION AND LANGUAGES

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Level of education of the producer

- None/Kindergarten
- Primary
- Secondaary
- University

Last class completed with succes in the primary school

- CI
- CP
- CE1
- CE2
- CM1
- CM2

Last class completed with succes in the secondary school

- 6e
- 5e
- 4e
- 3e
- 2nd
- 1ère
- Tle
- Autre

Last class completed with succes at University

- 1ère année
- 2ème année
- 3ème année
- 4ème année
- 5ème année
- 6ème année
- 7ème année
- 8ème année
- Autre

Specify Other class completed

Is the producer able to understand the local language?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to speak in local language?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to read in local language?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to write in local language?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to read in the local Swahili?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to write in the local Swahili?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to understand French?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to read in French?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to speak in French?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

Is the producer able to write in French?

- No ability
- Basic knowledge
- Good knowledge
- Fluent

EXPERIENCE WITH AGRICULTURE AND COTTON PRODUCTION

EXPERIENCE WITH AGRICULTURE AND COTTON PRODUCTION

For how many years has the producer taken agricultural production decision?

Record the number of year

For how many years has the producer taken cotton production decision?

Record the number of year

Which type of cotton has the producer grown in the most recent growing season?

- Only Conventional
- Only Organic
- Both

For how many years has the producer taken decisions regarding organic cotton production?

Is the producer a certified organic cotton producer?

- No
- Yes

For how many years has the cotton producer been a certified organic cotton producer?

Did the producer grow organic cotton in the past?

- No
- Yes

» Reason for non-trying of organic cotton production

First main reason you have never produced organic cotton

Second main reason you have never produced organic cotton

Third main reason you have never produced organic cotton

Fourth main reason you have never produced organic cotton

» Reason for abandoning organic cotton

When did you produce organic cotton for the very first time? (year)

Indicate the year

When did you stop producing organic cotton? (year)

Indicate the year

What is the first main reason you gave up organic cotton?

What is the second main reason you gave up organic cotton?

What is the third main reason you gave up organic cotton?

What is the fourth biggest reason you gave up organic cotton?

Were you the first member of your household who decided to grow organic cotton?

- No (other members of my household decided to grow organic cotton before I did)
- Yes (I was the first)

Did you have the option to join a programme for organic cotton in your local community?

- No
- Yes

Did you participate?

- No
 Yes

» Reasons for refusing to join a programme for organic cotton

First main reason for refusing to join a programme for organic cotton

Second main reason for refusing to join a programme for organic cotton

Third main reason for refusing to join a programme for organic cotton

Fourth main reason for refusing to join a programme for organic cotton

Do you know any organic cotton farmer in your local community?

- No
 Yes

Were you the first member of your household who decided to grow organic cotton?

- No (other members of my household decided to grow organic cotton before I did)
 Yes (I was the first)

PLOT-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS: NUMBER OF PLOTS

PLOT-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS: NUMBER OF PLOTS

Now we want to ask detailed information about all cotton plots managed by the producer in the most recent growing season (i.e. 2017/2018). If a plot is divided into different parts with different crops, please only consider together the parts grown with cotton.

How many organic cotton plots do you have?

How many conventional cotton plots do you have?

» What happened to the crop residues from the growing season 2016-2017 (e.g. stems, leaves, weeds) on your cotton plots?

1. burned

Did you burn crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2016-2017 agricultural campaign?

- No
 Yes

2. removed

Have crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2016-2017 cropping season been removed from the plot?

- No
 Yes

3. eaten by livestock on the plot

Have crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2016-2017 season been eaten by animals?

- No
 Yes

4. remained at the plot

Have crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2016-2017 crop been left on the plot?

- No
 Yes

PLOT-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

PLOT-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS: GENERAL INFORMATION

Now we want to ask you specific questions about each plot of cotton grown last season

» Information regarding cotton plot 1

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
 Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
- Partly owned and partly rented
- Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
- About the same
- Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
- Slightly sloped
- Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorbike
- Bus
- Car
- Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

Is there another cotton plot?

- No
- Yes

» Information regarding cotton plot 2

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
 Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
 Partly owned and partly rented
 Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
 About the same
 Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
 Slightly sloped
 Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
 Bicycle
 Motorbike
 Bus
 Car
 Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

Is there another cotton plot?

- No
- Yes

» Information regarding cotton plot 3

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
- Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
- Partly owned and partly rented
- Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
- About the same
- Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
- Slightly sloped
- Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorbike
- Bus
- Car
- Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

Is there another cotton plot?

- No
- Yes

» Information regarding cotton plot 4

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
- Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
- Partly owned and partly rented
- Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
- About the same
- Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
- Slightly sloped
- Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorbike
- Bus
- Car
- Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

Is there another cotton plot?

- No
- Yes

» Information regarding cotton plot 5

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
- Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
- Partly owned and partly rented
- Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
- About the same
- Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
- Slightly sloped
- Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorbike
- Bus
- Car
- Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

Is there another cotton plot?

- No
- Yes

» Information regarding cotton plot 6

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
- Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
- Partly owned and partly rented
- Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
- About the same
- Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
- Slightly sloped
- Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorbike
- Bus
- Car
- Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

Is there another cotton plot?

- No
- Yes

» Information regarding cotton plot 7

What have you produced on the first cotton plot, in the most recent growing season, i.e. 2017/18?

- Organic Cotton,
- Conventional Cotton

What is the size of cotton plot, in hectare?

Did you own or rent cotton plot?

- Owned
- Partly owned and partly rented
- Rented

What is the soil fertility of cotton plot, compared to the average soil fertility of other plots in your village?

Based on your appreciation

- Lower
- About the same
- Higher

What is the slope of cotton plot?

- Flat
- Slightly sloped
- Steeply sloped

How do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot?

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorbike
- Bus
- Car
- Other

Please describe how do you usually travel from your house to cotton plot.

What is the average travel time (in minutes) from your house to cotton plot, when you use the means of transport stated in the previous question?

CROPS IN THE MOST RECENT CROPPING SEASON (2016/17)

CROPS IN THE MOST RECENT CROPPING SEASON (2016/17)

Did you intercrop on your cotton plots?

- No
- On some cotton plots
- On all cotton plots

» Which crops did you intercrop with cotton on your plots?**1. Beans**

Did you associate cowpea / beans with cotton during the 2017-2018 campaign?

- No
- Yes

2. Sunflower

Did you associate the sunflower with cotton during the 2017-2018 campaign?

- No
- Yes

3. Vegetables

Did you associate vegetables with cotton during the 2017-2018 campaign?

- No
- Yes

4 Soybean

Did you associate soybeans with cotton during the 2017-2018 campaign?

- No
- Yes

5 Maize

Did you associate maize with cotton during the 2017-2018 campaign?

- No
- Yes

6 Other crops

Did you associate Other crops with cotton during the 2017-2018 crop year?

- No
- Yes

Please name all other crops that you intercropped with cotton on your plots.

Where there any other crops grown on your cotton plots? During the most recent growing season, e.g. at a part of the plot, before sowing cotton, or after harvesting cotton?

- No
- On some cotton plots
- On all cotton plots

Please explain in detail which other crops were grown when and where at your cotton plots during the most recent growing season.

CROPS IN THE CROPPING SEASON BEFORE (2015/16)

CROPS IN THE CROPPING SEASON BEFORE (2015/16)

Which crops/plants were grown on your cotton plots in the growing season before, i.e. 2016/17?

1. Bush (not cultivated for many years)

Was your cotton plot a Bush (not cultivated for many years) during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
- Yes

2. Fallow (weeds)

Was your cotton plot fallow during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
- Yes

3. Cotton

Did your cotton plot hold cotton during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
- Yes

4. Maize

Did your cotton plot hold corn during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
- Yes

5. Bean

Did your cotton plot hold cowpea / beans during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
- Yes

6. Sunflower

Did your cotton plot hold the sunflower during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
 Yes

7. Vegetable

Did you produced vegetables on your your cotton plot during 2016-17 agricultural campaign?

- No
 Yes

8. Other

What other crop did your cotton plot hold during the 2016-2017 crop year?

- No
 Yes

Please describe all other crops/plants were grown on your cotton plots in the growing season before, i.e. 2016/17.

What happened to the crop residues from the growing season 2016/15 (e.g. stems, leaves, weeds) on your cotton plots?

1. burned

Did you burn crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2015-2016 agricultural campaign?

- No
 Yes

2. removed

Have crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2015-2016 cropping season been removed from the plot?

- No
 Yes

3. eaten by livestock on the plot

Have crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2015-2016 season been eaten by animals?

- No
 Yes

4. remained at the plot

Have crop residues (stems, leaves, etc.) of the 2015-2016 crop been left on the plot?

- No
 Yes

LAND CLEARING

LAND CLEARING: DATES, TOOLS

When did you start the land clearing on your cotton plots?

yyyy-mm-dd

What tools or equipment were used for land clearing on your cotton plots?

1. Machete

- No
 Yes

2. Hand hoe

- No
 Yes

3. Other

- No
 Yes

Please describe the "other" tools or equipment that were used for land clearing on your cotton plots?

Did you own or rent the [answer to question EA3] that were used for land clearing on your cotton plots?

- All [answer to question EA3] were owned
 All [answer to question EA3] were rented
 The [answer to question EA3] were partly owned and partly rented

What were the total rental costs for the tools and equipment used for land clearing on your cotton plots?

LAND CLEARING: LABOUR (Salary can be paid in cash or in kind, in the latter case try to define a monetary value)

» How much hired labour for land clearing on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for land clearing on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for land clearing on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for land clearing on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

» How much family labour for land clearing on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

» How much family labour for land clearing on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

PLOUGHING

PLOUGHING: DATES, TOOLS

When did you do plough your cotton plots ?

yyyy-mm-dd

» What tools or equipment were used for ploughing your cotton plots ?

1. Tractor with Plough

 No Yes

2. Ox with plough

- No
- Yes

3. Hand hoe

- No
- Yes

4. Other

- No
- Yes

Please describe the "other" tools or equipment that were used for ploughing.

Did you own or rent the tractor and plough used for ploughing your cotton plots?

- All tractors and ploughs were rented
- The tractors and ploughs were partly owned and partly rented
- All tractors and ploughs were owned

Did you own or rent the ox and the plough for ploughing your cotton plots?

- All oxen and ploughs were owned
- All oxen and ploughs were rented
- The oxen and ploughs were partly owned and partly rented

Did you own or rent the [answer to question FA3] used for ploughing your cotton plots?

- All [answer to question FA3] were owned
- All [answer to question FA3] were rented
- The [answer to question FA3] were partly owned and partly rented

What were the total rental costs for all rented tools and equipment used for ploughing your cotton plots?

PLOUGHING: LABOUR (Salary can be paid in cash or in kind, in the latter case try to define a monetary value)

» How much hired labour for ploughing your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for ploughing your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for ploughing your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for ploughing your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for ploughing your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for ploughing your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

PLANTING

PLANTING: SEEDS**What was the source of the cotton seed you planted on your cotton plots ?**

- Government extension service
- Ginnery
- NGO / Private extension
- Local market
- Other

Please describe the source of the cotton seed planted on plot X as precise as possible (e.g. location of extension office or market, name of ginnery or seller, ...).

What is the Variety of the cotton planted on your cotton plots?

How did you pay for the cotton seed planted on your cotton plots?

- Purchased on cash
- Purchased on credit
- Exchanged
- Gift
- Other

Please describe how you paid for the cotton seed planted your cotton plots ?

What was the total cost of the seed planted on your cotton plots ?*If exchanged, include the approximate value of the exchange items*

PLANTING: DATES, METHODS, TOOLS**When was the cotton planted on your cotton plots?**yyyy-mm-dd

How was the cotton planted on your cotton plots?

- In rows
- Broadcasting
- Other

Please describe how the cotton was planted your cotton plots ?

What tools or equipment were used for planting cotton on your cotton plots ?

- No equipment
- Other

Please describe the tools and equipment that were used for planting cotton your cotton plots.

Did you own or rent the [answer to question GB5] that were used for planting cotton your cotton plots?

- All [answer to question GB5] were owned
- All [answer to question GB5] were rented
- The [answer to question GB5] were partly owned and partly rented

What were the total rental costs for all rented tools and equipment used for planting cotton your cotton plots ?

PLANTING: LABOUR (Salary can be paid in cash or in kind, in the latter case try to define a monetary value)

» How much hired labour for planting cotton your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for planting cotton your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for planting cotton your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for planting cotton your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for planting cotton your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for planting cotton your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

THINNING

THINNING: DATES, LABOUR (Salary can be paid in cash or in kind, in the latter case try to define a monetary value)

When did you do the thinning of cotton on plot X?

yyyy-mm-dd

» How much hired labour for thinning cotton your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for thinning cotton your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for thinning cotton your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for thinning cotton your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for thinning cotton your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for thinning cotton your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

WEEDING

WEEDING: DATES, TOOLS**When did you do the weeding on your cotton plots ?**yyyy-mm-dd

» What tools or equipment were used for the weeding on your cotton plots?**1. Hand hoes** No Yes**2. Ox-weeders** No Yes**3. Other** No Yes**Please describe the "other" tools or equipment that were used for the first weeding on your cotton plots .**

Did you own or rent the ox-weeders used for the weeding on your cotton plots? All ox-weeders were owned All ox-weeders were rented The ox-weeders were partly owned and partly rented**Did you own or rent the [answer to question IA3] used for the weeding of your cotton plots?** All [answer to question IA3] were owned All [answer to question IA3] were rented The [answer to question IA3] were partly owned and partly rented**What were the total rental costs for these equipments?**

WEEDING: LABOUR (Salary can be paid in cash or in kind, in the latter case try to define a monetary value)

» How much hired labour for the weeding of your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the weeding of your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the weeding of your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for the weeding of your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the weeding of your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the weeding of your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

CHEMICAL FERTILIZERS

CHEMICAL FERTILIZERS: TYPES, APPLICATIONS, QUANTITIES, SOURCES

Did you use NPK on your cotton plots?

Did you apply NPK?

- No
- Yes

» Detail on NPK used on cotton plots

How many times did you apply NPK?

» » At what dates did you apply NPK?

Date of the first application of NPK

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the second application of NPK

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the third application of NPK

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the fourth application of NPK

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of NPK was applied in total on all cotton plots? (kg)

» » Was NPK obtained at least partly from ...?

Government

No

Yes

Ginnery

No

Yes

Local market

No

Yes

Other

No

Yes

Please describe in detail all sources of NPK (e.g. location of government office or market, name of ginnery or seller, ...).

How much of NPK was obtained from the government? (kg)

What was the unit price of NPK obtained from the government? (FCFA/kg)

How much of NPK was obtained from a ginnery? (kg)

What was the unit price of NPK that was obtained from a ginnery? (FCFA/kg)

How much of NPK was obtained from a local market? (kg)

What was the unit price of NPK that was obtained from a local market? (FCFA/kg)

How much of NPK was obtained from other sources? (kg)

What was the unit price of NPK that was obtained from other sources? (FCFA/kg)

Please revise questions "JA5.1" and/or questions "JA8", "JA9", "JA10", until and "JA16" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + .

Did you use UREA on your cotton plots?

Did you apply UREA?

No

Yes

» Detail on UREA used on cotton plots

How many times did you apply UREA ?

» » At what dates did you apply UREA ?

Date of the first application of UREA

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the second application of UREA

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the third application of UREA

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the fourth application of UREA

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of UREA was applied in total on all cotton plots? (kg)

» » Was UREA obtained at least partly from ...?

Government

No

Yes

Ginnery

No

Yes

Local market

No

Yes

Other

No

Yes

Please describe in detail all sources of UREA (e.g. location of government office or market, name of ginnery or seller, ...).

How much of UREA was obtained from the government? (kg)

What was the unit price of UREA obtained from the government? (FCFA/kg)

How much of UREA was obtained from a ginnery? (kg)

What was the unit price of UREA that was obtained from a ginnery? (FCFA/kg)

How much of UREA was obtained from a local market? (kg)

What was the unit price of UREA that was obtained from a local market? (FCFA/kg)

How much of UREA was obtained from other sources? (kg)

What was the unit price of UREA that was obtained from other sources? (FCFA/kg)

Please revise questions "JA5.1" and/or questions "JA8", "JA9", "JA10", until and "JA16" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + .

Did you use Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots?

Did you apply [Other types of chemical fertilizer]?

No

Yes

» Detail on Other types of chemical fertilizer used on cotton plots

Please describe the chemical fertilizer (e.g., name).

How many times did you apply this chemical fertilizer ?

» » At what dates did you apply this chemical fertilizer ?

Date of the first application of this chemical fertilizer

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the second application of this chemical fertilizer

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the third application of this chemical fertilizer

yyyy-mm-dd

Date of the fourth application of this chemical fertilizer

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of this chemical fertilizer was applied in total on all cotton plots? (kg)

» » Was this chemical fertilizer obtained at least partly from ...?

Government

No

Yes

Ginnery

No

Yes

Local market

No

Yes

Other

No

Yes

Please describe in detail all sources of this chemical fertilizer (e.g. location of government office or market, name of ginnery or seller, ...).

How much of this chemical fertilizer was obtained from the government? (kg)

What was the unit price of this chemical fertilizer obtained from the government? (FCFA/kg)

How much of this chemical fertilizer was obtained from a ginnery? (kg)

What was the unit price of this chemical fertilizer that was obtained from a ginnery? (FCFA/kg)

How much of this chemical fertilizer was obtained from a local market? (kg)

What was the unit price of this chemical fertilizer that was obtained from a local market? (FCFA/kg)

How much of this chemical fertilizer was obtained from other sources? (kg)

What was the unit price of this chemical fertilizer that was obtained from other sources? (FCFA/kg)

Please revise questions "JA5.1" and/or questions "JA8", "JA9", "JA10", until and "JA16" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + .

NPK: LABOUR FOR THE APPLICATION

» How much hired labour for the application of NPK on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the application of NPK on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the application of NPK on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for the application of NPK on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the application of NPK on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the application of NPK on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

UREA: LABOUR FOR THE APPLICATION

» How much hired labour for the application of UREA on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the application of UREA on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the application of UREA on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for the application of UREA on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the application of UREA on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the application of UREA on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

Other types of chemical fertilizer: LABOUR FOR THE APPLICATION

» How much hired labour for the application of Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the application of Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for the application of Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for the application of Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for the application of Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» **How much family labour for the application of Other types of chemical fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by children?**

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

ORGANIC FERTILIZERS: TYPES, QUANTITIES, SOURCES

» **Type of organic fertilizer?**

Agribiofertilizer

No

Yes

Animal excreta / farm yard manure

No

Yes

Crop residues

No

Yes

Compost

No

Yes

Other

No

Yes

» **Details on Agribiofertilizer**

How many times did you apply Agribiofertilizer?

» » At what dates did you apply Agribiofertilizer?**First application**yyyy-mm-dd

Second applicationyyyy-mm-dd

Third applicationyyyy-mm-dd

Fourth applicationyyyy-mm-dd

How much of Agribiofertilizer was applied in total on all cotton plots?

Please, specify the unit in which you record this quantity

» » Was this Agribiofertilizer obtained at least partly from ...?**Market** No Yes**NGO** No Yes**Ginnery** No Yes**Own farm or made yourself** No Yes

Neighbours or other farmers No Yes**Other source** No Yes

Please describe in detail all sources of Agribiofertilizer (e.g. location of government office or market, name of ginnery or seller, ...).

» » Agribiofertilizer: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

How much of the Agribiofertilizer used on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

What was the unit price of the Agribiofertilizer you obtained from the market?

How much of the Agribiofertilizer was obtained from an NGO?

What was the unit price of the Agribiofertilizer that you obtained from an NGO?

How much of the Agribiofertilizer did you obtain from a ginnery?

What was the unit price of the Agribiofertilizer that you obtained from a ginnery?

How much of the Agribiofertilizer did you make yourself?

How much did you pay in total for the ingredients for the Agribiofertilizer applied on your cotton plots ?

How much of the Agribiofertilizer did you obtain from neighbours or other farmers?

How much did you pay in total to neighbours and other farmers for the Agribiofertilizer for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots ?

How much of the Agribiofertilizer did you obtain from other sources?

How much did you pay in total to other sources for the Agribiofertilizer for the application of organic fertilizers?

Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + +

» Agribiofertilizer: LABOUR FOR PREPARATION

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Agribiofertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Agribiofertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Agribiofertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Agribiofertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Agribiofertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Agribiofertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Agribiofertilizer: LABOUR FOR APPLICATION

» » How much hired labour for the application of Agribiofertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Agribiofertilizer on your cotton plots X was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Agribiofertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the application of Agribiofertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Agribiofertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Agribiofertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Details on [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]

How many times did you apply [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]?

» » At what dates did you apply [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]? (

First application

yyyy-mm-dd

Second application

yyyy-mm-dd

Third application

yyyy-mm-dd

Fourth application

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] was applied in total on all cotton plots?

Please, specify the unit in which you record this quantity

» » Was [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]obtained at least partly from ...?

Market

No

Yes

NGO

No

Yes

Ginnery

- No
 Yes

Own farm or made yourself

- No
 Yes

Neighbours or other farmers

- No
 Yes

Other source

- No
 Yes

Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + + +

» » [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

How much of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] used on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

What was the unit price of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] you obtained from the market?

How much of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] was obtained from an NGO?

What was the unit price of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] that you obtained from an NGO?

How much of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] did you obtain from a ginnery?

What was the unit price of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] that you obtained from a ginnery?

How much of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] did you make yourself?

How much did you pay in total for the ingredients for the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] applied on your cotton plots ?

How much of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] did you obtain from neighbours or other farmers?

How much did you pay in total to neighbours and other farmers for the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots ?

How much of the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] did you obtain from other sources?

How much did you pay in total to other sources for the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers?

Only if the answer to question KA5 is " Yes" is "1 Yes" AND the answer to question KA5.1 is unequal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11": Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question KA5.1 is equal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11".

» [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]: LABOUR FOR PREPARATION

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» [Animal excreta / farm yard manure]: LABOUR FOR APPLICATION

» » How much hired labour for the application of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] on your cotton plots X was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the application of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of [Animal excreta / farm yard manure] on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Details on Crop residues

How many times did you apply Crop residues?

» » At what dates did you apply Crop residues? (

First application

yyyy-mm-dd

Second application

yyyy-mm-dd

Third application

yyyy-mm-dd

Fourth application

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of Crop residues was applied in total on all cotton plots?

Please, specify the unit in which you record this quantity

» » Was Crop residues obtained at least partly from ...?

Market

- No
- Yes

NGO

- No
- Yes

Ginnery

- No
- Yes

Own farm or made yourself

- No
- Yes

Neighbours or other farmers

- No
- Yes

Other source

- No
- Yes

Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + + +

» » Crop residues: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

How much of the Crop residues used on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

What was the unit price of the Crop residues you obtained from the market?

How much of the Crop residues was obtained from an NGO?

What was the unit price of the Crop residues that you obtained from an NGO?

How much of the Crop residues did you obtain from a ginnery?

What was the unit price of the Crop residues that you obtained from a ginnery?

How much of the Crop residues did you make yourself?

How much did you pay in total for the ingredients for the Crop residues applied on your cotton plots ?

How much of the Crop residues did you obtain from neighbours or other farmers?

How much did you pay in total to neighbours and other farmers for the Crop residues for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots ?

How much of the Crop residues did you obtain from other sources?

How much did you pay in total to other sources for the Crop residues for the application of organic fertilizers?

Only if the answer to question KA5 is " Yes" is "1 Yes" AND the answer to question KA5.1 is unequal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11": Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question KA5.1 is equal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11".

» Crop residues: LABOUR FOR PREPARATION

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Crop residues] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Crop residues] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Crop residues] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Crop residues] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Crop residues] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Crop residues] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Crop residues: LABOUR FOR APPLICATION

» » How much hired labour for the application of Crop residues on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Crop residues on your cotton plots X was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Crop residues on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the application of Crop residues on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Crop residues on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Crop residues on your cotton plots was provided by children?**1. number of days**

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Details on [Compost]**How many times did you [Compost]?**

» » At what dates did you apply [Compost]? (**First application**

yyyy-mm-dd

Second application

yyyy-mm-dd

Third application

yyyy-mm-dd

Fourth application

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of [Compost] was applied in total on all cotton plots?

Please, specify the unit in which you record this quantity

» » Was [Compost] obtained at least partly from ...?**Market** No Yes**NGO** No Yes**Ginnery** No Yes**Own farm or made yourself** No Yes**Neighbours or other farmers** No Yes**Other source** No Yes

Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + + +

» » [Compost]: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

How much of the [Compost] used on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

What was the unit price of the [Compost] you obtained from the market?

How much of the [Compost] was obtained from an NGO?

What was the unit price of the [Compost] that you obtained from an NGO?

How much of the [Compost] did you obtain from a ginnery?

What was the unit price of the [Compost] that you obtained from a ginnery?

How much of the [Compost] did you make yourself?

How much did you pay in total for the ingredients for the [Compost] applied on your cotton plots ?

How much of the [Compost] did you obtain from neighbours or other farmers?

How much did you pay in total to neighbours and other farmers for the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots ?

How much of the [Compost] did you obtain from other sources?

How much did you pay in total to other sources for the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers?

Only if the answer to question KA5 is " Yes" is "1 Yes" AND the answer to question KA5.1 is unequal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11": Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question KA5.1 is equal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11".

» [Compost]: LABOUR FOR PREPARATION

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Compost] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Compost: LABOUR FOR APPLICATION

» » How much hired labour for the application of Compost on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Compost on your cotton plots X was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Compost on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the application of Compost on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Compost on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Compost on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Details on [Other Type of Fertilizer]

Please describe the organic fertilizer (e.g., name).

How many times did you apply this organic fertilizer?

» » At what dates did you apply this organic fertilizer? (

First application

yyyy-mm-dd

Second application

yyyy-mm-dd

Third application

yyyy-mm-dd

Fourth application

yyyy-mm-dd

How much of this organic fertilizer was applied in total on all cotton plots?

Please, specify the unit in which you record this quantity

» » Was this fertilizer obtained at least partly from ...?

Market

- No
 Yes

NGO

- No
 Yes

Ginnery

- No
 Yes

Own farm or made yourself

- No
 Yes

Neighbours or other farmers

- No
 Yes

Other source

- No
 Yes

Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question is equal to the sum of the answers to questions + + + + +

» » [Other Type of Fertilizer]: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

How much of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] used on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

What was the unit price of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] you obtained from the market?

How much of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] was obtained from an NGO?

What was the unit price of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] that you obtained from an NGO?

How much of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] did you obtain from a ginnery?

What was the unit price of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] that you obtained from a ginnery?

How much of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] did you make yourself?

How much did you pay in total for the ingredients for the [Other Type of Fertilizer] applied on your cotton plots ?

How much of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] did you obtain from neighbours or other farmers?

How much did you pay in total to neighbours and other farmers for the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots ?

How much of the [Other Type of Fertilizer] did you obtain from other sources?

How much did you pay in total to other sources for the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers?

Only if the answer to question KA5 is " Yes" is "1 Yes" AND the answer to question KA5.1 is unequal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11": Please revise questions "KA5.1" and/or questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11" so that the answer to question KA5.1 is equal to the sum of the answers to questions "KB1", "KB3", "KB5", "KB7", "KB9" and "KB11".

» **[Other Type of Fertilizer] : LABOUR FOR PREPARATION**

» » **How much hired labour for preparing the [[Other Type of Fertilizer]] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?**

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » **How much hired labour for preparing the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?**

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » **How much hired labour for preparing the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?**

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing the [Other Type of Fertilizer] for the application of organic fertilizers on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» Other Type of Fertilizer: LABOUR FOR APPLICATION

» » How much hired labour for the application of Other Type of Fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Other Type of Fertilizer on your cotton plots X was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the application of Other Type of Fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the application of Other Type of Fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Other Type of Fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of Other Type of Fertilizer on your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

Please, record all chemical herbicides used by the producer

CHEMICAL HERBICIDES USED

1

» CHEMICAL HERBICIDES: TYPES, QUANTITIES, SOURCES

* Type of chemical herbicides?

- Kalach / Round up (Glyphosate)
- Califor G
- Other

* Please describe the chemical herbicide (e.g., name).

* How many times did you apply this chemical herbicide ?

» » At what dates did you apply this chemical herbicide ? (Please specify the first date of each application)

* Date of the first application of chemical herbicide

yyyy-mm-dd

* Date of the second application of chemical herbicide

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the third application of chemical herbicide**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the fourth application of chemical herbicide**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **How much of this chemical herbicide was applied in total on all cotton plots?**

* **Please, specify the unit in which you record this quantity**

» » **Was this chemical herbicide obtained at least partly from ...?**

* **1 Government**

No

Yes

* **2 Cooperative**

No

Yes

* **3 Shop**

No

Yes

* **4 Market**

No

Yes

* **5 Other sources**

No

Yes

* **Please describe in detail all sources of this chemical herbicide (e.g. location of government office or market, name of ginnery or seller, ...).**

» **CHEMICAL HERBICIDES: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES**

* How much [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots obtained from the government?

* What was the unit price of the [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots obtained from the government?

* How much [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was obtained from a Cooperative?

* What was the unit price of the [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots obtained from a Cooperative?

* How much [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was obtained from a shop?

* What was the unit price of the [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots obtained from a shop?

* How much [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

* What was the unit price of the [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots obtained from the market?

* How much [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was obtained from other sources?

* What was the unit price of the [name of herbicide] for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots obtained from other sources?

» **CHEMICAL HERBICIDES: LABOUR**

» » **How much hired labour for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was provided by men?**

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » **How much hired labour for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was provided by women?**

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » **How much hired labour for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was provided by children?**

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the application of chemical herbicides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

Please, record all chemical insecticides used by the producer

All insecticides used by the producer

1

» CHEMICAL INSECTICIDES: TYPES, QUANTITIES, SOURCES

* Type of chemical insecticides?

- Cuter
- Sibemac
- Pyrenex
- Acer
- Other

* Please describe the chemical insecticide (e.g., name).

* How many times did you apply this chemical insecticide?

» » At what dates did you apply this chemical insecticide?

* Date of the first application of chemical insecticides

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the second application of chemical insecticides**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the third application of chemical insecticides**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the fourth application of chemical insecticides**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **How much of this chemical herbicide was applied in total on all cotton plots?**

* **Please specify the unit in which you record this quantity**

» » **Was this chemical insecticide obtained at least partly from...?**

* **1 Government**

No

Yes

* **2 Cooperative**

No

Yes

* **3 Shop**

No

Yes

* **4 Market**

No

Yes

* **5 Other sources**

No

Yes

- * Please describe in detail all sources of this chemical insecticide (e.g. location of government office or market, or seller, ...)
-

» **CHEMICAL INSECTICIDES: QUANTITIES AND PRICES FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES**

- * How much [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was obtained from the government?

- * What was the unit price of the [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots obtained from the government?

- * How much [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was obtained from the Cooperative?

- * What was the unit price of the [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots obtained from the Cooperative?

- * How much [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was obtained from a shop?

- * What was the unit price of the [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots obtained from a shop?

- * How much [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was obtained from the market?

- * What was the unit price of the [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots obtained from the market?

* How much [name of insecticide] for the application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was obtained from other sources?

* What was the unit price of the [name of insecticide] for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots obtained from other sources?

» CHEMICAL INSECTICIDES: LABOUR

» » How much hired labour for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the first application of chemical insecticides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

Please, record all chemical BIOPESTICIDES used by the producer

BIOPESTICIDES USED

1

» BIOPESTICIDES: TYPES, QUANTITIES, SOURCES

* Type of biopesticides ?

- Ready-made "industrial" biopesticide
- Home-made biopesticide (by the farmer or by others)
- Other

* Other": Please describe the biopesticide (e.g., name).

* How many times did you apply this biopesticide ?

» » At what dates did you apply this biopesticide ? (Please specify the first date of each application)

* **Date of the first application of this biopesticide**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the second application of this biopesticide**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the third application of this biopesticide**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **Date of the fourth application of this biopesticide**

yyyy-mm-dd

* **How much of this biopesticide was applied in total on all cotton plots?**

* **Please specify the unit in which you record this quantity**

» » **Was this biopesticide obtained at least partly from ...?**

* **1 produced by the farmer him/herself**

- No
 Yes

* **2 government**

- No
 Yes

* **3 market**

- No
 Yes

* **4 NGO**

- No
 Yes

*** 5 ginnery**

*

- No
 Yes

*** 6 neighbours or other farmers**

- No
 Yes

*** 7 other source**

- No
 Yes

*** Please describe in detail all sources of this biopesticide (e.g. location of government office or market, or seller, ...).**

*** What was the unit price of the biopesticide for the application of biopesticides on your cotton plots ?**

» » What were the ingredients of the biopesticide that was applied in the application of biopesticides on your cotton plots ?

*** 1 Urine**

- No
 Yes

*** 2 Soap**

- No
 Yes

*** 3 Pepper**

- No
 Yes

*** 4 Neem**

- No
 Yes

*** 5 Other**

- No
 Yes

* Please describe all "other" ingredients of the biopesticide that was applied in the application of biopesticides on your cotton plots .

* Did you purchase it or obtained it from nature?

- Purchased
- From nature
- Partly purchased and partly from nature
- Other

* Please specify the other source

* What did the producer spent in total on the ingredients of the biopesticide for the application of biopesticides on your cotton plots ?

* What is the total value representing the opportunity cost of ingredients collected from the wild?

» BIOPESTICIDES: LABOUR FOR PREPARATION

» » How much hired labour for preparing biopesticides for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing biopesticides for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for preparing biopesticides for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for preparing biopesticides for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing biopesticides for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for preparing biopesticides for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» BIOPESTICIDES: LABOUR FOR APPLICATION

» » How much hired labour for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

* 4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by men?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by women?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for the first application of biopesticides on your cotton plots was provided by children?

* 1. number of days

* 2. average hours per day

* 3. average number of workers

APPLICATION OF PESTICIDES (BOTH CHEMICAL PESTICIDES AND BIOPESTICIDES): TOOLS

**APPLICATION OF PESTICIDES (BOTH CHEMICAL PESTICIDES AND BIOPESTICIDES):
TOOLS**

» **What tools or equipment were used for applying pesticides (e.g. insecticides, herbicides, bio-pesticides) on your cotton plots?**

1. Sprayer machines

- No
 Yes

2. Other

- No
 Yes

Please describe the other tools or equipment used for applying pesticides on your cotton plots.

Did you own or rent the sprayer machines?

- All sprayer machines were owned
 All sprayer machines were rented
 The sprayer machines were partly owned and partly rented

Did you own or rent the Other equipment used?

- All [answer to OA2] were owned
 All [answer to OA2] were rented
 The [answer to OA2] were partly owned and partly rented

What were the total rental costs for these equipments?

For all applications with rented equipments

**APPLICATION OF PESTICIDES (BOTH CHEMICAL PESTICIDES AND BIOPESTICIDES):
HEALTH ASPECTS**

Did the persons who sprayed the pesticides or biopesticides receive training on pest and diseases management in cotton farming?

- None of the persons
- Some of the persons
- All of the persons

» From whom did these persons receive training on pest and diseases management?

1 Government

- No
- Yes

2 Cooperative

- No
- Yes

3 NGO

- No
- Yes

4 Other sources

- No
- Yes

Please describe in detail all sources of the training that the persons received on pest and diseases management

Did the persons who sprayed the pesticides or biopesticides receive training on handling and disposing of pesticides or biopesticides?

- None of the persons
- Some of the persons
- All of the persons

» From whom did the persons receive training on handling and disposing of pesticides or biopesticides?

1 Government

- No
- Yes

2 Cooperative No Yes**3 NGO** No Yes**4 Other sources** No Yes

Please describe in detail all sources of the training that the persons received on handling and disposing of pesticides or biopesticides

Did the persons who sprayed the pesticides or biopesticides usually bath after spraying?

 No Yes

Did the persons who sprayed the pesticides or biopesticides usually eat while spraying?

 No Yes

Does he wash his hands?

 No Yes

How does he wash his hands?

 With water only With water and soap With water and ash Other

Please describe how he washes his hands

» Which protective equipment did the persons who sprayed the pesticides or biopesticides wear while spraying?

1 Long trousers No Yes**2 Overall** No Yes**3 Coat** No Yes**4 Boots** No Yes**5 Gloves** No Yes**6 Goggles** No Yes**7 Masks** No Yes**8 Other** No Yes

Please describe all "other" protective equipment that the persons who sprayed the pesticides or biopesticides wore while spraying?

APPLICATION OF PESTICIDES (BOTH CHEMICAL PESTICIDES AND BIOPESTICIDES): ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS

How were the containers of the pesticides and biopesticides disposed?

1 left on the plot

- No
- Yes

2 thrown into the bush

- No
- Yes

3 buried

- No
- Yes

4 thrown in a river or stream

- No
- Yes

5 burned

- No
- Yes

6 reused for household purposes

- No
- Yes

7 disposed in a natural hole, gully or crevasse

- No
- Yes

8 Other

- No
- Yes

Please describe how the containers of pesticides and biopesticides were disposed.

HARVESTING

HARVESTING: NUMBER OF TIMES HARVESTED

How many times did you harvest cotton on your cotton plots ?

» **HARVESTING: DATES, LABOUR (Salary can be paid in cash or in kind, in the latter case try to define a monetary value)**

When was the first time that cotton on your plots was harvested?

yyyy-mm-dd

When was the second time that cotton on your plots was harvested?

yyyy-mm-dd

When was the third time that cotton on your plots was harvested?

yyyy-mm-dd

When was the fourth time that cotton on your plots was harvested?

yyyy-mm-dd

» » **How much hired labour for harvesting cotton on your plots was provided by men?**

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » **How much hired labour for harvesting cotton on your plots was provided by women?**

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much hired labour for harvesting cotton on your plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» » How much family labour for harvesting cotton on your plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for harvesting cotton on your plots was provided by women?**1. number of days**

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» » How much family labour for harvesting cotton on your plots was provided by children?**1. number of days**

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

HARVESTING: QUANTITIES**How much cotton did you harvest on all your cotton plots ? (kg)***Note: the answer should also include cotton that was not sold due to too low quality, contamination, losses, theft, etc.*

HARVESTING: TRANSPORTATION**To which destination did you transport the cotton from your cotton plots after harvest?**

- All cotton directly to the household
- All cotton directly to the collection point
- Partly from the plot to household and partly to the collection point

Did you rent a vehicle for transporting the cotton from your cotton plots to the household?

- No
- Yes

What were the costs of renting a vehicle for transporting the cotton from your cotton plots to the household?

Did you rent a vehicle for transporting the cotton from your cotton plots to the collection point?

- No
 Yes

What were the costs of renting a vehicle for transporting the cotton from your cotton plots to the collection point?

Did you rent a vehicle for transporting the cotton harvested on your cotton plots from the household to the collection point?

- No
 Yes

What were the costs of renting a vehicle for transporting the cotton harvested on your cotton plots from the household to the collection point?

HARVESTING: COTTON CLEANING AND SORTING

How much of your cotton was cleaned before it was sold?

- None
 A small part
 About half
 Most
 All

How much of your cotton was sorted for quality before selling?

- None
 A small part
 About half
 Most
 All

HARVESTING: LABOUR FOR COTTON CLEANING AND SORTING

» How much hired labour for cleaning and sorting cotton from your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for cleaning and sorting cotton from your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much hired labour for cleaning and sorting cotton from your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

4. total wage paid

» How much family labour for cleaning and sorting cotton from your cotton plots was provided by men?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for cleaning and sorting cotton from your cotton plots was provided by women?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

» How much family labour for cleaning and sorting cotton from your cotton plots was provided by children?

1. number of days

2. average hours per day

3. average number of workers

Cotton sales: date, storage

What is the date of the sale?

yyyy-mm-dd

Storage: Where did you store the largest part of seed cotton before sale?

- Field
- House
- Primary market in the (sub-)village
- Collection point in the (sub-)village
- No storage, immediate transportation from the field to the collection point
- Warehouse
- Other

Please describe where you stored the largest part of the cotton before sale.

How long time did you store the seed cotton at this place before sale? (consider the cotton that was stored there for the longest time)

Indicate the number of days

How much of your cotton did you store or transport at least for some time in polypropylene bags?

- None
- A small part
- About half
- Most
- All

As what type of cotton did you sell your cotton?

- Conventional cotton
- Organic cotton under conversion
- Certified organic cotton

Cotton sales: dates, storage, buyer

How many times have you sold your cotton in the most recent growing season?

What is the date of each sale?

Storage: Where did you store the largest part of seed cotton before the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Field
- House
- Collection point
- No storage, immediate transportation from the field to the collection point
- Other

Please describe where you stored the largest part of the cotton before the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton.

How long time did you store the seed cotton at this place before the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton? (consider the cotton that was stored there for the longest time)

As what type of cotton did you sell your cotton at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Conventional cotton
- Organic cotton under conversion
- Certified organic cotton

Please describe the buyer of the Xst/nd/th sale of your cotton (e.g. location, name of company, name of agent, ...).

What was the main reason for choosing this buyer for the Xst/nd/th sale of your cotton?

- I received a loan from this buyer which required that I sell my cotton to him/her.
- I had a contract with this buyer (without loan).
- I (almost) always sell my cotton to this buyer.
- This buyer offered the highest price.
- This buyer grades my cotton as highest quality.
- This buyer accepts cotton with quality issues (e.g. contamination)
- Other

Please describe the main reason for choosing this buyer for the Xst/nd/th sale of your cotton.

Cotton sales: quantities, grading

What quantity of quality A cotton did you sell?

What quantity of quality B cotton did you sell?

What was the reason for downgrading the cotton to quality B?

- Contaminated with polypropylenes
- Contaminated with sand and stones
- Contaminated with water
- Sticky cotton
- Immature cotton
- Colour
- Other

Please describe the reason for downgrading the cotton to quality B

Are you satisfied with the grading of your cotton?

- Very much satisfied
- satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- dissatisfied
- Very much dissatisfied

Cotton sales: quantities, grading

What quantity of quality A cotton did you sell at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

What quantity of quality B cotton did you sell at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

What was the reason for downgrading the cotton to quality B at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Contaminated with polypropylenes
- Contaminated with sand and stones
- Contaminated with water
- Sticky cotton
- Immature cotton
- Colour
- Other

Please describe the reason for downgrading the cotton to quality B at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton

Are you satisfied with the grading of your cotton at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Very much satisfied
- satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- dissatisfied
- Very much dissatisfied

Cotton sales: prices and revenues

What unit price did you receive for your quality A cotton?

Please specify the unit in which you record this quantity

What unit price did you receive for your quality B cotton?

Please specify the unit in which you record this quantity

Are you satisfied with the price that you obtained?

- Very much satisfied
- satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- dissatisfied
- Very much dissatisfied

What is your total gross revenue?

What is the amount subtracted for repayment of inputs credits?

Did you actually receive minus FCFA?

- No
- Yes

How much did you actually receive?

Cotton sales: prices and revenues**What unit price did you receive for your quality A cotton at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?**

What unit price did you receive for your quality B cotton at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

How was the price settled for the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- The price was publicly announced by the buyer.
- The price was negotiated with the buyer at the time of selling.
- The price was agreed upon with the buyer in advance.
- Other

Please describe how the price was settled for the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

Are you satisfied with the price that you received for the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Very much satisfied
- satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- dissatisfied
- Very much dissatisfied

What is your total gross revenue of the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

What is the amount subtracted for repayment of inputs credits at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

Did you actually receive minus \${PIT7} Tsh?

- No
- Yes

Cotton sales: rejected cotton

Was some of your cotton initially rejected by the cotton buyer?

- No
- Yes

What quantity was initially rejected?

What was the reason for the initial rejection?

- Contaminated with polypropylenes
- Contaminated with sand and stones
- Contaminated with water
- Immature cotton
- Colour
- Other

Please describe the reason for the initial rejection.

What did you do with the initially rejected quantity?

- Cleaned it and delivered it later
- Sold it to other farmers, e.g. for animal feeding
- Gave it to my own animals
- Threw it away
- Put it on my land as a source of organic fertilizer
- Other

Please describe what you did with the initially rejected quantity of cotton

How much money did you receive from selling the initially rejected cotton to another farmer? (FCFA)

Cotton sales: rejected cotton**Was some of your cotton initially rejected by the cotton buyer at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?**

- No
- Yes

What quantity was initially rejected at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

What was the reason for the initial rejection at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Contaminated with polypropylenes
- Contaminated with sand and stones
- Contaminated with water
- Immature cotton
- Colour
- Other

Please describe the reason for the initial rejection at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton.

What did you do with the initially rejected quantity at the Xst/nd/th sale of cotton?

- Cleaned it and delivered it later
- Sold it to other farmers, e.g. for animal feeding
- Gave it to my own animals
- Threw it away
- Put it on my land as a source of organic fertilizer
- Other

Please describe what you did with the initially rejected quantity of cotton.

Sold it to other farmers": How much money did you receive from selling the initially rejected cotton to another farmer?

Please make sure that the selling of the initially rejected cotton is reported in one of the following cotton sales. Please change the answer to question PG0 if necessary.

CREDIT

CREDIT

Did anyone in this household get cash loan during agricultural acmpaign 2017-2018?

- No
- Yes

Now we will record all the credits / loans you have had during the 2017-2018 agricultural campaign

» Credit received in agricultural campaign 2017-2018

*** When did you receive the cash? (Month)**

- January
- February
- March
- April
- May
- Juine
- Juilly
- August
- September
- October
- November
- Décembre

*** What was the amount of this loan they received in cash? (Francs CFA)**

*** From who did you get your loan**

- Government Microfinance institution
- Private Microfinance institution
- Neighbors
- Other

*** Please specify the other source of loan**

*** Do you have to pay interest on this loan?**

- No
- Yes

*** 2.a. percent interest per year OR**

*** 2.b. interest amount last 12 month**

* How much have you already paid back? (1. Francs CFA)

* When was the loan paid back to the lending institution? (Month)

* How much do you still have to repay back? (Francs CFA)

EXTENSION SERVICES

EXTENSION SERVICES

During the most recent growing season (2017/18)

Have you received any extension services?

During 2017/18 agricultural campaign

No

Yes

Did you receive any extension service regarding cotton production or marketing?

During 2017/18 agricultural campaign

No

Yes

» From whom did you receive extension advice regarding cotton production or marketing during the most recent growing season?

1 Public extension services

No

Yes

2 Cooperative / farmers' village groups

No

Yes

3 Ginneries

- No
 Yes

4 Input traders

- No
 Yes

5 Fellow farmers

- No
 Yes

6 NGO

- No
 Yes

7 Brochure and leaflets

- No
 Yes

8 Other

- No
 Yes

Please describe in detail all providers of extension service (e.g. locations, names of organisations, names of officers/consultants, ...).

» Regarding what aspects of cotton production did you receive extension services?**1 Land preparation (e.g. ploughing)**

Did you received extension services on "Land preparation (e.g. ploughing)" during agricultural campaign 2017/18?

- No
 Yes

2 Sowing (e.g. seeds)

Did you received extension services on "Sowing (e.g. seeds)" during agricultural campaign 2017/18?

- No
 Yes

3 Fertility management (fertiliser application, crop rotation, tree protection, erosion control)

Did you received extension services on "Fertility management" during agricultural campaign 2017/18?

No

Yes

4 Pest management / crop protection

Did you received extension services on "Pest management / crop protection" during agricultural campaign 2017/18?

No

Yes

5 Weed management / Weeding

Did you received extension services on "Weed management / Weeding " during agricultural campaign 2017/18?

No

Yes

6 Harvest and quality control

Did you received extension services on "Harvest and quality control" during agricultural campaign 2017/18?

No

Yes

7 Other

Did you received extension services on other aspects?

No

Yes

Please describe the "Other" aspects of extension service.

During the growing season before (2016/17)

Have you received any extension services?

During 2016/17 agricultural campaign

No

Yes

Did you receive any extension service regarding cotton production or marketing?

During 2016/17 agricultural campaign

No

Yes

» From whom did you receive extension advice regarding cotton production or marketing during the most recent growing season?

1 Public extension services

No

Yes

2 Cooperative / farmers' village groups

No

Yes

3 Ginneries

No

Yes

4 Input traders

No

Yes

5 Fellow farmers

No

Yes

6 NGO

No

Yes

7 Brochure and leaflets

No

Yes

8 Other

No

Yes

Please describe in detail all providers of extension service (e.g. locations, names of organisations, names of officers/consultants, ...).

» Regarding what aspects of cotton production did you receive extension services?

1 Land preparation (e.g. ploughing)

Did you received extension services on "Land preparation (e.g. ploughing)" during agricultural campaign 2016/17?

No

Yes

2 Sowing (e.g. seeds)

Did you received extension services on "Sowing (e.g. seeds)" during agricultural campaign 2016/17?

No

Yes

3 Fertility management (fertiliser application, crop rotation, tree protection, erosion control)

Did you received extension services on "Fertility management" during agricultural campaign 2016/17?

No

Yes

4 Pest management / crop protection

Did you received extension services on "Pest management / crop protection" during agricultural campaign 2016/17?

No

Yes

5 Weed management / Weeding

Did you received extension services on "Weed management / Weeding " during agricultural campaign 2016/17?

No

Yes

6 Harvest and quality control

Did you received extension services on "Harvest and quality control" during agricultural campaign 2016/17?

No

Yes

7 Other

Did you received extension services on other aspects?

No

Yes

Please describe the "Other" aspects of extension service.

MEMBERSHIPS IN GROUPS OR ORGANISATIONS

MEMBERSHIPS IN GROUPS OR ORGANISATIONS

Of which groups or organisations are you a member?

a. Conventional cotton producer group

- No
 Yes

b. Organic cotton producer group

- No
 Yes

c. Tontine group

- No
 Yes

d. Group of mutual aid / solidarity

- No
 Yes

e. other

- No
 Yes

Other organization

Advantages and disadvantages of the two types of cotton production

Now, we ask you what you think are the advantages and disadvantages of organic and conventional cotton production for you as a cotton farmer. There are no right or no wrong answers. We just want to know your personal opinion as an expert regarding cotton production on your farm.

Which type of cotton production do you think is on average more suitable for your plots (considering the soil characteristics, prevalence of weeds and pests, etc. of all your plots that are suitable for cotton production)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

For which type of cotton do you think it is easier for your household to get sufficient funds for buying inputs (e.g. seeds, fertilizer, pesticides, hired labour)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton do you think is easier to produce for your household (e.g. burden and type of manual work, management)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think is better for the health of the workers on your cotton plots (including you and your family)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think is better for the natural environment (e.g. rivers, wild plants and animals)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think gives your household more independence (e.g. from credit grantors, input providers, cotton buyers, hired labourers, farmers' groups, etc.)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think gives your household a higher (cash) income?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think gives your household more stable (cash) income, i.e. a lower risk of crop failures and low incomes in some years?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think gives you a higher esteem from people around you (e.g. your friends, neighbours, extension officers, village leaders)?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Which type of cotton production do you think gives you a higher satisfaction with the (seed) cotton that you have produced?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Considering all advantages and disadvantages, which type of cotton production do you think gives you and your household in general a better life?

- Organic much better
- Organic somewhat better
- Organic slightly better
- About the same
- Conventional slightly better
- Conventional somewhat better
- Conventional much better

Life Satisfaction indicators

Overall, How satisfied are you (individually) with your life?

From 0 not satisfied to 10 completely satisfied

Overall, describe the level of your (individually) Health status (from 0 bad to 10 very good)

From 0 not satisfied to 10 completely satisfied

Overall, describe how recognized is your (individually) work by the local community in the village (from not recognised 0 to 10 fully recognised)

From 0 not satisfied to 10 completely satisfied

Overall, describe how satisfied are you (individually) with your relationship with neighbors (from not satisfied 0 to 10 fully satisfied)

From 0 not satisfied to 10 completely satisfied

Overall, how satisfied are you (individually) with your work(from not satisfied 0 to 10 fully satisfied)

From 0 not satisfied to 10 completely satisfied

GPS Cordinates of the main house of the household

Please stay about 3 meters from the main entrance of the house. Make sure the sky is clear (i.e, dot not stay under a tree or under shelter)

latitude (x.y °)

longitude (x.y °)

altitude (m)

précision (m)

Questionnaire completed on DATE

The date you finished the questionnaire

yyyy-mm-dd

Questionnaire completed on TIME

Indicate the hour you finished the questionnaire

hh:mm

Please, record a line between GPS coordinates of the producer's and his cotton farm

GPS coordinates can only be collected when outside.

latitude (x.y °)

longitude (x.y °)

altitude (m)

précision (m)

[KML](#)**Please, record the area of cotton farm**

This will record a polygon of multiple GPS coordinates; the last point is the same as the first point.

latitude (x.y °)

longitude (x.y °)

altitude (m)

précision (m)

[KML](#)

fermer le polygone

Take a picture of the coton farm

Cliquez ici pour téléverser un fichier. (< 5MB)

Supervisor